

Interrogating the Spatio-Temporal Dynamics of Urban Footfall using Principal Component Analysis

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Summary

As more and more of the world's population move to urban areas, understanding pedestrian dynamics becomes increasingly important. Data sources that measure pedestrian counts offer great potential as a means of interrogating urban flows without needing to track individuals.

This study attempts to better understand the fundamental spatio-temporal structures that characterise aggregate pedestrian behaviour. It employs Principal Component Analysis to distill the key temporal elements that comprise aggregate daily pedestrian activity across the city. We identify clear, distinct components that represent different types of activities and can be used to characterise different types of neighbourhood.

KEYWORDS: Urban Data Science; Footfall; Principal Component Analysis (PCA); Pedestrian Dynamics.

1 Introduction

The UN have projected that that nearly two-thirds of the global population will reside in cities by 2050 (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, 2018). As cities become larger and more dense there is a clear need to better understand and predict urban dynamics, including pedestrian movement patterns. However, quantifying and modelling the dynamics of large-scale pedestrian movements – i.e. the flows of people around cities – is challenging. Reliable data for capturing large-scale pedestrian behaviours has traditionally been scarce. Furthermore, the inherent complexity of daily urban dynamics, where large numbers of individuals pursue unique goals and actions, makes it challenging to identify distinct behaviours from aggregate data.

In this paper we use Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to isolate and analyse the key temporal elements that comprise aggregate daily pedestrian activity across a city. We use data from the city of Melbourne, Australia, where a large volume of pedestrian count data from a variety of sensors

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across the city are publicly available. We illustrate that the main components that arise from a PCA are indicative of clear, distinct behaviours (commuting, leisure, etc.). Furthermore, we show that by studying the change in the loadings of these components over time we can chart the evolution of the types of activities that characterise different locations in the build environment.

2 Data

Our study focuses on Melbourne, Australia, making use of the extensive high-resolution data available at the City of Melbourne Open Data Portal. This portal offers detailed hourly pedestrian counts from 94 sensors that are usually placed under awnings or on street poles, to monitor foot-path activity. Figure 1 displays sensor locations. While some sensors have been active since 2009, others were installed later, and certain sensors lack complete historical data. Here we use two full years worth of data for 2018 and 2019. This period was chosen because it contains the largest volume of count data as more sensors have been added over time, but is also not affected by the COVID pandemic that began in 2020 and significantly disrupted ‘normal’ urban activities.

Figure 1: Locations of the pedestrian counting sensors in Melbourne.

3 Method: Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique used for reducing the dimensionality of a data table – i.e. a table where each row (observation) can be described by a number of distinct columns (variables). PCA transforms the table into a new set of variables that encapsulate the most significant features, known as the ‘principal components’. Each observation can then be approximated through a linear combination of these principal components and specific component ‘loadings’ (coefficients). For a full introduction the interested reader can refer to Abdi and Williams (2010) or Jolliffe (2011).

To prepare our data, we extract the hourly counts from each sensor for each day in our 2-year study period, removing any sensor-day observations that are missing counts for one or more hours.

This results in a data table with 36958 rows, where each observation (row) represents the hourly footfall for a particular sensor on a particular day. The table has 24 variables (columns), each representing an hourly count. A single observation can therefore be thought of as a single point in a 24-dimensional point cloud. In PCA, the principal components can then be thought of as ‘directions’ in this space; where each direction is necessarily a 24-item vector. These directions are arranged so the first explains most data variation and subsequent ones progressively less. After PCA the original observations can then be approximated by combining these components with a unique set of ‘loadings’ (coefficients).

It is necessary to decide on the number of components to use. If we were to use 24 components in our PCA, then each original observation could be perfectly recreated by simply assigning loadings that are equal to the original data. This, however, defeats the purpose of PCA, whose aim is to replicate the original data reasonably well with fewer components, thus reducing dimensions. Figure 2 illustrates the ‘proportion of explained variance’ that quantifies how much of the total variance each principal component captures. With only three components, 95% of the variation in the original data can be captured. Therefore in the remainder of the paper we concentrate on the first three components as these represent the clearest behavioural patterns.

Figure 2: Cumulative explained variance ratio: with only 3 components it is possible to explain 95% of the variance in the original footfall data.

4 Results: Components as Insight into Urban Dynamics

Figure 3 presents the main PCA result. The top subfigure illustrates the mean footfall pattern for all sensors and all days. The pattern is typical of many cities, with peaks in the morning, midday and afternoon. It is important to note that weekends show quite different patterns, so we also analyse *weekly* footfall, but those results are not discussed here. The most striking observation from Figure 3 is that the first three components represent very clear, distinct types of activity.

Figure 3: The mean footfall pattern (top image) and first three components (bottom images).

Component 1 is almost identical to the mean daily activity. Hence rather than representing any specific activity, this component quantifies the average *busyness* of a location. Sensor-day observations that are busy will have loadings for this component that are greater than one, or between zero and one for those sensor-days that are quieter than the average.

Component 2 is distinguished by large peaks in the early morning and late afternoon. These correspond closely to the typical ‘rush hour’ commuting times that would be expected in Melbourne. Hence observations with large loadings for this component will be indicative of times and locations that have large commuting populations.

Component 3 suppresses activity in the middle of the day. This raises a useful point: as the loadings assigned to a component can be negative, an observation that exhibited an *increase* in lunchtime footfall might have a negative loading for this component.

Overall, these three components appear to be associated with different types of activity in the city. Therefore it is possible to explore them in more detail to further interrogate the different types of activities that might take place at different locations. A full exploration is beyond the scope of this short paper, but Figure 4 hints at the type of insight that is possible. It illustrates the size of the contributions that the different components for one location (Southbank) make across the two years of our study. Interestingly there appears to be a drop in footfall at the beginning of 2019, but this only affects the first component ('busyness'). Hence although the location becomes less busy, this is not as a result of a change in the numbers of commuters or lunch-time visitors specifically. In other locations it is possible to identify changes in the second and third components that suggest the activities that take place in that location are genuinely changing over time.

Figure 4: The contributions of different components. The top figure illustrates the mean weekly footfall at the location and the bottom figures illustrate the size of the three components make for the 'Southbank' location over 2 years

5 Conclusions

This paper has presented the use of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to explore the spatio-temporal dynamics of footfall patterns in Melbourne, Australia. The most striking result is the clarity with which some of the derived components appear to represent typical urban behaviours. Future work will continue to explore these components with an aim to better understanding the value of PCA as a tool to understand the dynamic and evolving footfall patterns in cities.

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